

ProCleanLakes

Readme file

**202051110-ProCleanLakes-
Determination of selected
environmental pollutants in lake
water and sediment by advanced
analytical instrumental methods-V01**

**Funded by
the European Union**

Project: 101157886 | HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01-04 | www.procleanlakes.eu

Creator: Maja Mikulić, Sanda Rončević, University of Zagreb, Trg Republike Hrvatske 14 10000 Zagreb, Croatia

Reason(s) for data analysis: the data was used to write master thesis of Maja Mikulić

The data was collected within project ProCleanLakes. The data presents Master thesis, which include results of chemical analysis of sediment samples from project's Monitoring site 1 (Vransko lake).

Creation date of file(s): 11/2025

Used method(s): *analytical chemistry methods (instrumental analysis ICP-MS, GC-MS), chemometric methods*

Used software (incl. version and add-ons) and tools:

- *Statistica TIBCO 14.1*
- *Microsoft Office*

Data:

- *20250714-ProCleanLakes-Determination of selected environmental pollutants in lake water and sediment by advanced analytical instrumental methods-V01.pdf*

Code:

Additional files: none

License:

All data, files and codes are licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC BY 4.0) <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Notes: none